

Light emitting biosilica by *in vivo* functionalization of *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* diatom microalgae with organometallic complexes

Danilo Vona¹, Roberta Ragni^{*1}, Emiliano Altamura¹, Paola Albanese¹, Michelaria Giangregorio², Stefania Roberta Cicco³, Gianluca Maria Farinola^{1*}

¹ Chemistry Department, University of Bari "Aldo Moro", Via Orabona 4, Bari 70126, Italy

² Chemistry Department, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche-Istituto di Nanotecnologia (CNR-Nanotec), Via Orabona 4, Bari 70126, Italy

³ Chemistry Department, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche-Istituto di Chimica dei Composti OrganoMetallici (CNR-ICCOM), Via Orabona 4, Bari 70126, Italy

* Correspondence: *gianlucamaria.farinola@uniba.it; roberta.ragni@uniba.it

Abstract: *In vivo* incorporation of a series of organometallic photoluminescent complexes in *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* diatoms' shells (frustules) is investigated as a biotechnological route to luminescent biosilica nanostructures. [Ir(ppy)₂bpy]⁺[PF₆]⁻ [(2,2'-bipyridine)bis(2-phenylpyridinato)iridium(III) hexafluorophosphate], [Ru(bpy)₃]²⁺ 2[PF₆]⁻ [tris(2,2'-bipyridine)ruthenium(II) hexafluorophosphate], AlQ₃ (tris-(8-hydroxyquinoline)aluminum), ZnQ₂ (bis-8-hydroxyquinoline-zinc) are used as model complexes to explore the potentiality and generality of the investigated process. The luminescent complexes are added to diatoms culture and the resulting luminescent silica nanostructures are isolated by an acid-oxidative treatment that removes the organic cells matter without altering both frustules morphology and photoluminescence of incorporated emitters. Results show that, except for ZnQ₂, the protocol successfully leads to the incorporation of complexes into the biosilica. Spontaneous self-adhering ability of both bare and doped *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* cells on conductive indium tin oxide (ITO) coated glass slides is observed, which can be exploited to generate dielectric biofilms of living microorganisms with luminescent silica shells. In general, this protocol can be envisaged as a profitable route to new functional nanostructured materials for photonics, sensing or biomedicine *via in vivo* chemical modification of diatom frustules with organometallic emitters.

Keywords: microalgae; diatoms; frustules; biosilica; luminescence; transition metal complexes

1. Introduction

Diatoms microalgae have recently attracted particular interest of materials scientists since they can be envisaged as bio-factories for products of mesoporous biosilica with morphology hardly reproducible by human technologies.[1] Diatoms' silica cell walls (frustules) are composed of valves and girdles with shape, dimension and highly periodic nanostructure strictly dependent on the microalgal species.[2] Current literature shows the suitability of diatom frustules or their components for applications in various fields, e.g. as natural photonic crystals and lenses in optics,[3, 4] biocompatible porous scaffolds for drug delivery and biomedicine,[5-9] nanostructured templates for generation of highly porous conducting materials in electronics. [10] Several approaches for chemical modification of diatoms biosilica for specific applications have been developed.[11] Surface chemical modification [12-13] of frustules after cleaning from the organic cell matter represents a common route to biosilica-based materials for sensing or catalysis. [14] Isolation of diatoms'

biosilica shells and their bioclastic conversion into nanostructures with replicated morphology but completely different chemical composition has been used to develop conducting functional nanomaterials for electronics. [15]

Although less widely explored so far, a further method of functionalization consists in the *in vivo* incorporation of tailored molecules added to the algal culture. In this case, molecules are up-taken by living cells and conveyed inside their silica deposition vesicles (SDVs), [16] where they are involved into the biosilicification process that generates frustules. This approach has been mainly used to investigate frustule's morphogenesis, and a rather limited number of fluorescent organic dyes has been employed for this aim so far. [17, 18]

The benefit of the *in vivo* incorporation method lies in the possibility to get in straightforward way, wheter compared to the genetic engineering approach, biohybrid materials combining the functions of incorporated molecules with the properties deriving from frustules nanostructure. A proof of this concept was recently provided by our group, by *in vivo* incorporation of an aryleneethynylene blue fluorophore into frustules of centric *Thalassiosira weissflogii* diatoms with average 11 μm valve diameter and 20 nm pore size, yielding luminescent biosilica structures whose photonic properties result from the modulation of the dye photoluminescence by the photonic nanopatterned silica structures. [19]

We also recently demonstrated the *in vivo* incorporation of $[\text{Ir}(\text{ppy})_2\text{bpy}]^+[\text{PF}_6]^-$ complex into frustules of *Thalassiosira weissflogii* diatoms: hybrid phosphorescent organic/inorganic nanoclusters composed of Ir-doped biosilica nanoparticles trapped within a residual portion of organic cell matter were isolated by ultracentrifugation of doped diatoms after removal of the majority of the organic cell matter with a soft acid/oxidative treatment. [20] In this case, a harsh acid/oxidative ($\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{HCl}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$) protocol, despite being more efficient in purifying the silica shells, was not applied since it degraded the photoluminescent complex. This biotechnological route to luminescent silica nanoparticles is more eco-sustainable than synthetic methods. However, in view of pursuing biohybrid materials for photonics, it would be strongly desirable to achieve higher purity degree of the metal-doped biosilica, keeping unaltered both the structural properties of the integer silica shells and the photoluminescence of the incorporated organometallic complexes.

In the search of a more general protocol, here we explore the *in vivo* incorporation of a series of four organometallic complexes in *Phaeodactylum tricornerutum*, a pennate diatom with rafe dimension of $\sim 12 \mu\text{m}$. *Phaeodactylum tricornerutum* is a model semi-benthic, adherent microalgal species, studied as an ecologically and biologically relevant model species. Its genome, biomineralization and adhesion properties are well established [21]. Besides the orange emitting $[\text{Ir}(\text{ppy})_2\text{bpy}]^+[\text{PF}_6]^-$, already investigated for *Thalassiosira weissflogii*, the red phosphor $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+} 2[\text{PF}_6]^-$ was used as a further model complex with similar octahedral structure, to explore possible effects of a different transition metal ion [Ru(III) vs Ir(III)] on the incorporation into diatoms. We also extended our study to neutral commercially available AlQ_3 and ZnQ_2 complexes, widely used as both electron

transporting and green or yellow light emitting materials for optoelectronics, respectively. [22-28] Except for ZnQ₂, the complexes were successfully incorporated into frustules and viability tests on cell cultures revealed a good level of biocompatibility, since doped diatoms were still capable of colonizing flat surfaces and forming biofilms. The photoluminescence of incorporated emitters was retained even after harsh acid/oxidative (H₂SO₄, HCl/H₂O₂) purification cycles, leading to highly purified valves with integer nanostructure and preserved metal complex photoluminescence.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

Ultrapure grade acetone, ethanol, sulfuric acid, dimethyl sulfoxide, [Ru(bpy)₃]²⁺ 2[PF₆]⁻, AlQ₃ and ZnQ₂ were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Germany). [Ir(ppy)₂bpy]⁺ [PF₆]⁻ was synthesized according to the literature. [29]

2.2 Methods

Bidimensional fluorescence images of living diatoms and frustules were recorded by an Axiomat microscope Zeiss (German), using a TRITC-filter set ($\lambda_{exc} = 540$ nm, $\lambda_{emi} > 590$ nm) for detection of [Ru(bpy)₃]²⁺ 2[PF₆]⁻ and a combination of FITC-filter ($\lambda_{exc} = 465$ nm, $\lambda_{emi} > 525$ nm) and DAPI-filter (blue passband) for [Ir(ppy)₂bpy]⁺[PF₆]⁻, AlQ₃ and ZnQ₂. A confocal laser scanning microscope Leica SP8 X with upright configuration was used for photophysical and morphological characterization: 3D and λ scan images were performed using a UV/Diode laser with 405 nm or 488 nm excitation wavelength and a HC PL APO CS2 63x/1.40 oil objective. Emission spectra were recorded in the 450-700 nm spectral range. This interval was divided into 36 detection steps with 5 nm step size. FTIR-ATR spectra were acquired with a Perkin Elmer Spectrum Two Spectrophotometer equipped with a 2 × 2 mm diamond crystal. Spectra were recorded in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ with a 2 cm⁻¹ resolution, using 0.25 cm⁻¹ acquisition interval and acquiring 32 scans for each sample. Raman spectra were collected using a LabRAM HR Horiba-Jobin Yvon spectrometer with 532 nm excitation laser.

2.3 Diatoms cultures

Phaeodactylum tricornutum diatoms (CCAP strain 1055) were cultured inside a vertical incubator in polystyrene (PS) flasks (250 mL) using sterile seawater mixed with f/2 Guillard solution (buffered with NaOH at pH 7.8) and sodium metasilicate. Growth and adhesion were monitored at 18-22°C, 65% relative humidity, under a continuous Photon Flux Density (PFD) provided by one cool white fluorescent tube. The light/dark-cycle of 14/8 h was employed. Partial medium change was set every 2 weeks, while total f/2 Guillard solution change was set every 1 month.

2.4 In vivo functionalization with organometallic emitters

For *in vivo* incorporation experiments, a 3 mM stock solution of each organometallic complex in dimethylsulfoxide (1 mL) was prepared. The stock solutions (15 μ L) were then diluted with sterile fresh medium (1.5 mL) in 75 mL PS flasks and, after gently stirring, 1.5 mL of the algal culture (cell density 5 × 10⁶ cells/mL) was added to each flask. The *in vivo*

incorporation experiment was carried out using 15 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ concentration of the organo-metallic complex in the cell culture sample and controlling the culture at 1, 4 and 7 days after the addition of the emitter. For adhesion experiments, 3 mL of algal culture samples were tested using ITO substrates ($1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$) in PS multiwells.

2.5 Purification of doped frustules

After 7 days of doping, glass conic tubes were used to collect and wash repeatedly cells (2200 rpm, 12'). After the last centrifugation, cells were suspended in bi-distilled water (500 μL) and treated with a mixture of H_2SO_4 (50 μL), HCl (34%, 50 μL) and H_2O_2 (3x50 μL). Cleaning mixtures were kept for 1 h at 55 $^\circ\text{C}$ and the procedure was repeated 3 times. Then, precipitation of doped biosilica occurred by sedimentation. After removal of supernatants, and various washing cycles with distilled water (250-500 μL), all samples were deposited on a glass slide, heated to favor the solvent evaporation and finally subjected to microscopy observation.

3. Results

3.1 Photostability of organometallic complexes in the culture medium

The chemical structures of the luminescent complexes used in this study are reported in Figure 1. Their photostability in the aqueous solution used as the culture medium for the cells was evaluated before starting the staining experiments.

Figure 1 Chemical structures of organometallic complexes.

Complexes were dissolved in DMSO (30 μL ; 3.37 mM) and the organic solution was poured into f/2 Guillard medium (3 mL) at pH 5.5. [30] Figure 2a shows the emission spectra recorded immediately after the preparation of all solutions. The resulting emission colours are also shown in the images of solutions in Figure 2b. Figure 2c reports the decay of the intensity of maximum photoluminescence of each complex at 1, 2, 4 and 8 h after the preparation of solutions, with the aim to evaluate the photostability of complexes emission in time intervals long enough to let *in vivo* incorporation to start in diatoms microalgae.

Figure 2. a) Emission spectra of complexes in *f/2* Guillard medium at $t=0$; b) Images of solutions of complexes in DMSO/ *f/2* Guillard medium; c) Variation of percentages of maximum photoluminescence intensity of complexes' solutions recorded at 0, 1, 2, 4, 8 h time intervals.

3.2 *In vivo* incorporation of complexes in diatoms

Phaeodactylum tricornutum diatoms were cultured in sterile sodium metasilicate enriched seawater composed of *f/2* Guillard solution with nutrients. *In vivo* staining was carried out according to the procedure reported in the Materials and Method Section. A TRITC filter was used to detect the red emission of both chloroplasts and $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$, whereas emission of $[\text{Ir}(\text{ppy})_2\text{bpy}]^+$, AlQ_3 and ZnQ_2 was observed by a combination of DAPI/FITC filters. Bidimensional fluorescence microscopy images recorded in merge mode for bare and doped *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* cells at 1, 4 and 7 days after the addition of complexes are shown in Figure 3.

164

165

166

167

168

169

170

171

172

173

174

175

176

177

Figure 3. Bidimensional fluorescence microscopy images (in merge mode) of *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* cells in (a) the control sample and after addition of (b) $[\text{Ir}(\text{ppy})_2\text{bpy}]^+$, (c) $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$, (d) AlQ_3 and (e) ZnQ_2 . TRITC and DAPI-filtered images were detected in merge mode for the control sample and diatoms doped with Ir, Al and Zn complexes, while TRITC-filtered fluorescence was used for cells treated with Ru complex. Images are detected after (i) 1, (ii) 4 and (iii) 7 days. Scale bars: 20 μm .

178

179

180

181

182

183

184

3.3 Diatoms adhesion on ITO substrates

185

To indirectly assess the viability of *P. tricornutum* and at the same time to evaluate their film forming property, the adhesion of cells on conductive substrates was investigated. Both pristine cells and cells doped with Ir, Ru and Al complexes were let to adhere on conductive Indium-Tin Oxide $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ coated glass slide. Adhesion was analysed using confocal microscopy and cells were visualized using bright field (DIC mode). Samples were firstly flushed pipetting with fresh medium, in order to leave only the strongly adhered cell portion on the substrate surface. Adhesion was monitored at 1, 4 and 7 days (Figure 4).

186

187

188

189

190

191

192

193

Figure 4. Bright Field (DIC mode) microscopy images for chloroplasts of (a) bare, (b) Ir-doped, (c) Ru-doped, (d) Al-doped cells adhered on conductive ITO substrates at (i) 1, (ii) 4 and (iii) 7 days after immersion of the substrate in cells culture samples. Scale bars: 50-100 μm .

194
195
196
197

3.4 Purification and characterization of doped biosilica

198
199
200
201

Figures 5*i* show confocal microscopy images with 3D reconstruction of living bare and living cells doped with iridium, ruthenium and aluminum complexes, while Figures 5*ii* report fluorescence bidimensional microscopy images of bare and doped shells isolated after harsh acid-oxidative treatment of diatoms, based on the use of sulfuric acid 10% V/V chloridric acid 10% V/V and hydrogen peroxide 10%V/V at 55°C for 60'.

202
203
204
205
206

207

Figure 5. 3D-confocal reconstruction images of (i) living diatoms (a: bare, b: Ir-doped, c: Ru-doped, 208
 d: Al-doped cells); (ii) bidimensional fluorescence microscopy images of bare and doped frustules 209
 after acid-oxidative treatment. 210

Figure 6 shows the photoluminescence spectra recorded, by confocal microscopy, exciting an entire 212
 valve of each sample of purified Ir- Ru- and Al-doped biosilica and excluding any aggregate. 213
 Images of doped valves and neat solid films of complexes were obtained by bidimensional 214
 fluorescence microscopy and reported in insets of Figure 6. 215

217

218

Figure 6. Photoluminescence spectra recorded *via* confocal microscopy of: (continuous line) purified (a) Ir-doped (b) Ru-doped, (c) Al-doped valves and (dotted lines) neat films of the relative complexes. Inset images report the analysed valves (top) and the neat films (bottom) of complexes recorded by bidimensional fluorescence microscopy.

221

222

223

Efficacy of the cleaning protocol of biosilica was also demonstrated via Fourier Transformed Infrared-Attenuated Total Reflectance (FTIR-ATR) spectroscopy (Figure 7) and Raman spectroscopy was also suitable to confirm the presence of signals belonging to coordination transitions between metal and non-metal atoms in doped biosilica (Figure 8).

224

225

226

227

228

229

Figure 7. ATR spectra of (a) dried cells after recovery from culture medium (fresh diatoms) and after purification with acid-oxidative protocol of (b) bare, (c) Ir-doped, (d) Ru-doped, (e) Al-doped shells.

230

231

Figure 8. Raman spectra of biosilica shells isolated from bare diatoms (grey line), Ir- (red line), Ru- (blue line) and Al- (green line) doped diatoms.

4. Discussion

The organometallic complexes used as model dopants are reported in Figure 1. Starting from our previous study on centric *Thalassiosira weissflogii* diatoms, we firstly selected $[\text{Ir}(\text{ppy})_2\text{bpy}]^+[\text{PF}_6]^-$ to explore its suitability for doping another microalgal species such as the *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* pennate diatom. Moreover, $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+} 2[\text{PF}_6]^-$ was selected with the aim of exploring the possibility to extend the incorporation protocol to another complex with analogous cationic octahedral structure, but different in the nature of transition metal ion. We further investigated the suitability of the doping method for other neutral complexes, such as AlQ_3 and ZnQ_2 , selected as commercially available organometallic dopants, [26, 27, 31] for applications in optoelectronics. Emission spectra recorded for complexes in f/2 Guillard medium show an orange luminescence peaked at 587 nm ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 375$ nm) for $[\text{Ir}(\text{ppy})_2\text{bpy}]^+$ whereas a typical red photoluminescence was observed for $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ ($\lambda_{\text{emi}} = 607$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 463$ nm). Yellow and green emission were recorded for AlQ_3 ($\lambda_{\text{emi}} = 491$ nm and 531 nm, $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 380$ nm) and ZnQ_2 ($\lambda_{\text{emi}} = 489, 512, 535$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 380$ nm), respectively (Figure 2a).

The photostability of emission of the complexes in the cells culture medium was initially demonstrated in the absence of the cells, in 8h time period (Figure 2c), long enough to let *in vivo* incorporation to start in diatom microalgae. In fact, complexes mainly penetrate inside diatoms in the first day of their addition to cultures. Profiles of emission spectra were retained during the photostability study, with quenching percentages of luminescence intensities after 8 h of 40 ± 12 for $[\text{Ir}(\text{ppy})_2\text{bpy}]^+$, 5 ± 3 for $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$, 19 ± 6 for AlQ_3 and 15 ± 3 for ZnQ_2 (Figure 2c).

Considering the limited reduction of photoluminescence intensity and retention of emission spectra profiles, all complexes were explored for feeding experiments.

Diatoms were therefore exposed to solutions of organometallic emitters at different concentration (10 μM , 15 μM and 20 μM), to evaluate incorporation of the complexes. However, the precipitation of emitters at 20 μM and the reduced complexes photoluminescence at 10 μM limited the study to 15 μM as the suitable value of concentration of all complexes as feeding agents.

Incorporation of the complexes was investigated via bidimensional fluorescence microscopy of bare and doped *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* cells at 1, 4 and 7 days after the addition of the organometallic emitters (Figure 3).

As expected, chloroplasts in untreated cells of the control sample appeared as strongly red emitting mottles that increase in density from the first to the fourth day of detection, with organization of cells in clusters at the 7th day (Figures 3a). Red emitting chloroplasts were also evident in all dispersions of cells treated with organometallic complexes, even 7 days after their addition, this showing the healthy state of diatoms during the complex incorporation (Figures 3b-e).

Figure 3bi shows that $[\text{Ir}(\text{ppy})_2\text{bpy}]^+$ penetrates in the cells during the first day, whereas no emission was found in the external medium. The yellow-orange photoluminescence of the complex was still observed both in protoplasm and in frustules 7 days after its addition (Figures 3bii, 3biii).

Both $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ and AlQ_3 were found to penetrate only in frustules (Figures 3c, 3d and insets). Moreover, in the case of doping with $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$, an increase of doped cells density was observed passing from 1 to 7 days (Figures 3c). Insets of Figures 3b-d show incorporation of Ir, Ru and Al emitters into biosilica shells. Conversely, ZnQ_2 did not penetrate inside cells, and so we concluded that it is not suitable for *in vivo* incorporation. This could be in principle due to a strong Zn complex-complex aggregation in solution, leading to a decrease of its bioavailability.

Cells viability was also investigated indirectly exploring the biological property of *Ph. Tricornutum* diatoms to adhere on substrates. This study interesting to further demonstrate the possibility to easily form biofilms of microorganisms doped with luminescent organometallic complexes onto indium tin oxide based conductive substrates.

As shown in Figure 4, bare cells increased their density on glass substrates in 4 days, clustering at 7 days of culture. Conversely, iridium and aluminum doped cells formed smaller clusters due to cell-cell interactions. Ruthenium doped cells appeared as adherent cells, but they lost the capability of forming cell clusters, likely due to a decrease of cell-cell interaction in the suspension as a possible defence mechanism.

After the *in vivo* incorporation, two methods of purification were tested to remove the organic matter and retain the luminescence of complexes into biosilica shells, thus recovering luminescent valves with retained morphology. A soft purification protocol reported by Kroger *et al.*, [32] based on washing with sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS 5% V/V) and ethylene diamino tetraacetic acid (EDTA 100 mM) for 15' at 60°C did not successfully remove the chloroplasts and the organic protoplasm from biosilica. Contrary to our previous results reported for *Thalassiosira weissflogii* frustules, a harsh cleaning protocol based on sulfuric acid 10% V/V, chloridric acid 10% V/V and hydrogen peroxide 10%V/V, at 60°C for 30', turned out to be very efficient to remove the protoplasm and chloroplasts and purify the Ir, Ru and Al-doped biosilica samples, after *in vivo* incorporation experiments.

In living diatoms, red chloroplasts only contributed to the red emission of bare cells (Figure 5ai) while the iridium complex stained silica and its emission was also localized in chloroplasts (Figure 5bi). In the case of Ru and Al doped cells, some empty cells (insets in Figures 5ci, 5di) and chloroplast-active cells were observed (Figures 5ci, 5di). After three cycles of acid-oxidative treatment, empty stained valves incorporating the complexes

were isolated and spotted over glass slides (Figure 5bii, 5cii, 5dii). Control valves exhibited a weak blue autofluorescence mainly due to silica and residual organic matter (Figure 5aii).

Confocal microscopy was also used to record photoluminescence spectra for each sample of doped biosilica after purification, with the aim to compare them with those of neat films of the organometallic complexes. All samples were obtained after 7 days of feeding. Emission spectra were recorded in the 450-750 nm spectral range, exciting ($\lambda_{exc} = 405$ nm) entire valves. In all cases, the photoluminescence of complexes inside doped valves is slightly blue shifted versus that of the neat film of complex (Figures 6a-c), likely due to an effect of entrapment of complexes in the silica bulk or of interaction between the complex photoluminescence and the silica nanostructure or reduced aggregation compared to the complex as a neat film. As shown in the insets of Figure 7, all purified luminescent valves retained their morphological integrity.

Evidence of the efficacy of the cleaning procedure of biosilica valves was also given by Fourier Transformed Infrared-Attenuated Total Reflectance (FTIR-ATR) spectroscopy (Figure 7). In all samples of purified bare and doped biosilica, as an effect of the acid-oxidative treatment, the $-C=O$ stretching contribution at 1750 cm^{-1} was strongly decreased with respect to living diatoms, whereas the Si-O stretching signal at 1150 cm^{-1} was more evident. The aliphatic $-CH$ symmetric and asymmetric stretching signals, near 3000 cm^{-1} , almost disappeared after purification. [6]

Raman spectroscopy was also used to check for specific signals diagnostic for coordination transitions between metal and non-metal atoms in doped biosilica (Figure 7). These signals were found in diatoms shells treated with organometallic complexes and were absent in untreated biosilica. Figures 7a and 7b show Raman spectra of bare biosilica (black line), Al- (green line), Ru- (blue line) and Ir- (red line) doped shells in two different energy ranges, $100\text{-}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $130\text{-}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$, to highlight spectral regions where metal-ligand modes can be detected. Two prominent bands are observed in the spectrum of bare biosilica, at $\sim 560\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to Si-O-Si stretching vibrations, and at $\sim 1100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to SiO/SiO₂ symmetric stretching. Shoulders at 350 cm^{-1} , 480 cm^{-1} and 950 cm^{-1} are attributed to O-Si-O deformation, O₃SiOH tetrahedral vibrations and SiO₃/SiO₂ symmetric stretching, respectively. [33]. The bands at $\sim 800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to SiO₄ symmetric stretching. In $1250\text{-}1900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range $-CH_2$, $-CH_3$, $-C-C-$ bands are evident while the C-H stretching vibration appears in the range between $2800\text{-}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to a not complete removal of aromatic and aliphatic carbon sources eventually associated to biosilica even after the cleaning treatment. The Raman spectrum of shells doped with Al complex, exhibits several modes in the range of $150\text{-}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which are assigned to Al-O framework vibrations, at 506 cm^{-1} and 754 cm^{-1} are attributed to a ν_3 and ν_1 [AlO₄⁵⁻] respectively. [34] Three metal-ligand modes can be observed for Ru-doped biosilica, at 456 cm^{-1} and $370\text{-}376\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to ν (Ru-N) modes and at 248 cm^{-1} due to ν (N-Ru-N) mode.[35] For Ir-treated shells, ν (Ir-C,N) bands are very weak and can be detected in the range $193\text{-}324\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The inset in Figure 8 highlights ν (Ir-C,N) bands. [36].

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, we have investigated *in vivo* incorporation of iridium, ruthenium, aluminum and zinc luminescent organometallic complexes into *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* diatom microalgae. Except for ZnQ₂, the complexes penetrate cells and stain frustules without altering diatoms viability even 7 days after their addition. The microalgal species still retains its capability of adhesion by cell-cell and cell-substrate interactions after the uptake of the organometallic emitters, thus forming luminescent biofilms of living microorganisms. Moreover, a hard acid-oxidative treatment, based on sulfuric acid, chloridric acid and hydrogen peroxide, of doped diatoms allows isolation of biosilica valves retaining both their pristine nanostructured morphology and the emission properties of

the incorporated transition metal complex. The evidence of incorporation of complexes into frustules was provided by confocal and bidimensional fluorescence microscopies as well as by FTIR-ATR and Raman spectroscopies. This biotechnological protocol represents a straightforward method of preparation of biosilica doped with luminescent organometallic complexes, with the benefit of easily achieving silica nanostructures, never reported so far, that combine photoluminescence of organometallic complexes with structural properties of diatom valves optimized by Nature in billion years. Moreover, the film forming properties of the semi-benthonic diatom used can be exploited to self-assemble *in vivo* thin films of doped biosilica. Although the reasons why ZnQ₂ is not suitable as dopant for *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* are not clarified, our results show the suitability of the method for preparation of light emitting iridium, ruthenium and aluminum doped biosilica valves with integer nanostructure and can pave the way to a variety of biohybrid materials for photonics and optoelectronics.

Author Contributions: Danilo Vona contributed to diatoms culture and feeding experiments; Roberta Ragni contributed to complex synthesis and characterization, experimental design and paper writing; Emiliano Altamura and Paola Albanese performed confocal microscopy analysis; Michelaria Giangregorio contributed to Raman analysis; Stefania Roberta Cicco contributed to the spectroscopic characterization of biosilica; Gianluca Maria Farinola contributed to planning all the experiments and paper writing.

Funding: This research was funded by the European Commission through EU project 800926-HyPhOE (Hybrid Electronics based on Photosynthetic Organisms), H2020-MSCA-ITN-2019 project 860125 - BEEP (Bio-inspired and bionic materials for enhanced photosynthesis).

Data Availability Statement: Data is contained within the article or supplementary material.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Graphical Abstract:

References

- Ragni, R.; Cicco, S. R.; Vona, D.; Leone, G.; Farinola, G. M. Biosilica from diatoms microalgae: smart materials from biomedicine to photonics. *J. Mater. Res.* **2017**, *32*(2), 279–291.
- Hildebrand, M.; Lerch, S.J.L.; Shrestha, R.P. Understanding Diatom Cell Wall Silicification—Moving Forward. *Front. Mar. Sci.* **2018**, *5*, 1–19.
- Ferrara, M.A.; Dardano, P.; De Stefano, L.; Rea, I.; Coppola, G.; Rendina, I.; Congestri, R.; Antonucci, A.; De Stefano, M.; De Tommasi, E. Optical Properties of Diatom Nanostructured Biosilica in *Arachnoidiscus* sp: Micro-Optics from Mother Nature. *PLoS One* **2014**, *9*, e103750.
- Fuhrmann, T.; Landwehr, S.; El Rharbi-Kucki, M.; Sumper, M. Diatoms as living photonic crystals. *Appl. Phys. B* **2004**, *78*, 257–260.
- Vona, D.; Leone, G.; Ragni, R.; Palumbo, F.; Evidente, A.; Vurro, M.; Farinola, G.M.; Cicco, S.R. Diatoms biosilica as efficient drug-delivery system. *MRS Adv.* **2015**, *1*, 3825–3830.

6. Cicco, S. R.; Vona, D.; De Giglio, E.; Cometa, S.; Mattioli Belmonte, M.; Palumbo, F.; Ragni, R.; Farinola, G. M. Chemically Modified Diatoms Biosilica for Bone Cell Growth with Combined Drug-Delivery and Antioxidant Properties. *ChemPlusChem* **2015**, *80*(7), 1104–1112. 401–403
7. Cicco, S. R.; Vona, D.; Gristina, R.; Sardella, E.; Ragni, R.; Lo Presti, M.; Farinola, G. M. Biosilica from Living Diatoms: Investigations on Biocompatibility of Bare and Chemically Modified *Thalassiosira weissflogii* Silica Shells. *Bioengineering* **2016**, *3*, 1–19. 404–406
8. Ragni, R.; Cicco, S. R.; Vona, D.; Leone, G.; Farinola, G. M. Biosilica from diatoms microalgae: smart materials from biomedicine to photonics. *J. Mater. Res.* **2017**, *32*, 279–291. 407–408
9. Cicco, S.R.; Vona, D.; Leone, G.; De Giglio, E.; Bonifacio, M.A.; Cometa, S.; Fiore, S.; Palumbo, F.; Ragni, R.; Farinola, G.M. In vivo functionalization of diatom biosilica with sodium alendronate as osteoactive material. *Mat. Sci and Eng.: C* **2019**, *104*, 109897. 409–411
10. Pan, Z.; Lerch, S.J.L.; Xu, L.; Li, X.; Chuang, Y.-J.; Howe, J.Y.; Mahurin, S.M.; Dai, S.; Hildebrand, M. Electronically transparent graphene replicas of diatoms: a new technique for the investigation of frustule morphology. *Sci. Rep.* **2014**, *4*, 1–6. 412–413
11. Ragni, R.; Cicco, S.; Vona, D.; Farinola, G.M. Multiple Routes to Smart Nanostructured Materials from Diatom Microalgae: A Chemical Perspective. *Adv Mater.* **2018**, *30*, e1704289. 414–415
12. Vona, D.; Lo Presti, M.; Cicco, S. R.; Palumbo, F.; Ragni, R.; Farinola, G. M. Light emitting silica nanostructures by surface functionalization of diatom algae shells with a triethoxysilane functionalized π -conjugated fluorophore. *MRS Adv.* **2016**, *1*, 3817–3823. 416–418
13. Vona, D.; Cicco, S. R.; Ragni, R.; Leone, G.; Lo Presti, M.; Farinola, G. M. Biosilica/polydopamine/silver nanoparticles composites: new hybrid multifunctional heterostructures obtained by chemical modification of *Thalassiosira weissflogii* silica shells. *MRS Commun.* **2018**, *8*, 911–917. 419–421
14. Fischer, C.; Adam, M.; Mueller, A.C.; Sperling, E.; Wustmann, M.; van Pée, K.-H.; Kaskel, S.; Brunner, E. Gold Nanoparticle-Decorated Diatom Biosilica: A Favorable Catalyst for the Oxidation of d-Glucose. *ACS Omega* **2016**, *1*, 1253–126. 422–423
15. Ragni, R.; Cicco, S.R.; Vona, D.; Farinola, G.M. Nanostructured Silica from Diatoms Microalgae: Smart Materials for Photonics and Electronics. In *Green Materials for Electronics*, Irimia-Vladu, M.; Glowacki, E.D.; Sariciftci, N.S.; Bauer, S.; Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, 2018; Volume 1, Chapter 11, pp. 287–313. 424–426
16. Poulsen, N.; Kröger, N. J. Silica Morphogenesis by Alternative Processing of Silaffins in the Diatom *Thalassiosira pseudonana*. *J. Biol. Chem.* **2004**, *279*, 42993–42999. 427–428
17. Kucki, M.; Fuhrmann-Lieker, T. Staining diatoms with rhodamine dyes: control of emission colour in photonic biocomposites. *J. R. Soc. Interface* **2012**, *9*, 727–733. 429–430
18. Lo Presti, M.; Ragni, R.; Vona, D.; Leone, G.; Cicco, S.; Farinola, G. M. In vivo doped biosilica from living *Thalassiosira weissflogii* diatoms with a triethoxysilyl functionalized red emitting fluorophore. *MRS Adv.* **2018**, *3*, 1509–1517. 431–432
19. Ragni, R.; Scotognella, F.; Vona, D.; Moretti, L.; Altamura, E.; Ceccone, G.; Mehn, D.; Cicco, S. R.; Palumbo, F.; Lanzani, G.; Farinola, G. M. Hybrid Photonic Nanostructures by In Vivo Incorporation of an Organic Fluorophore into Diatom Algae. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2018**, *28*, 1706214. 433–435
20. Della Rosa, G.; Vona, D.; Aloisi, A.; Ragni, R.; Di Corato, R.; Lo Presti, M.; Cicco, S. R.; Altamura, E.; Taurino, A.; Catalano, M.; Farinola, G. M. Luminescent silica based nanostructures from in vivo Iridium-doped diatoms microalgae, *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.* **2019**, *7*, 2207–2215. 436–438
21. Yang, M.; Lin, X.; Liu, X.; Zhang, J.; Ge, F. Genome Annotation of a Model Diatom *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* Using an Integrated Proteogenomic Pipeline. *Mol. Plant.* **2018**, *11*, 1292–1307. 439–440
22. Brütting, W.; Frischeisen, J.; D. Schmidt, T.; Scholz, B.J.; Mayr, C. Device efficiency of organic light-emitting diodes: Progress by improved light outcoupling, *IPSS* **2013**, 44–65. 441–442
23. Mróz, W.; Ragni, R.; Galeotti, F.; Mesto, E.; Botta, C.; De Cola, L.; Farinola, G. M.; Giovanella, U. Influence of electronic and steric effects of substituted ligands coordinated to Ir(III) complexes on the solution processed OLED properties. *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2015**, *3*, 7506–7512 (2015). 443–445
24. Ragni, R.; Maiorano, V.; Pugliese, M.; Maggiore, A.; Orselli, E.; Babudri, F.; Gigli, G.; De Cola, L.; Farinola, G. M. A highly fluorinated iridium complex as a blue-green emitting component for white electroluminescence. *Synth. Met.* **2017**, *227*, 148–155. 446–448
25. Ragni, R.; Punzi, A.; Babudri, F.; Farinola, G.M. Organic and Organometallic Fluorinated Materials for Electronics and Optoelectronics: A Survey on Recent Research. *EurJOC.* **2018**, *2018*, 3500–3519. 449–450
26. Collins, A.M.; Olof, S.M.; Mitchelsa, J.M.; Mann, S. Facile preparation and processing of aqueous dispersions of tris(8-hydroxyquinoline) aluminium(III) photoluminescent nanoparticles. *J. Mater. Chem.* **2009**, *19*, 3950–3954. 451–452
27. Pan, H.-C.; Liang, F.-P.; Mao, C.-J.; Zhu, J.-J.; Chen, H.-Y. Highly Luminescent Zinc(II)-Bis(8-hydroxyquinoline) Complex Nanorods: Sonochemical Synthesis, Characterizations, and Protein Sensing. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2007**, *111*, 20, 5767–5772. 453–454

28. Carreño, A.; Páez-Hernández, D.; Zúñiga, C.; Ramírez-Osorio, A.; Nevermann, J.; Rivera-Zaldívar, M. M.; Otero, C.; A. Fuentes, J. Prototypical cis-ruthenium(II) complexes present differential fluorescent staining in walled-cell models (yeasts). *Chemical Papers* **2019**, *73*, 1629–1637. 455
456
457
29. Schneider, G.E.; Bolink, H.J.; Constable, E.C.; Ertl, C.D.; Housecroft, C.E.; Pertegàs, A.; Zampese, J.A.; Kanitz, A.; Kessler, F.; B. Meier., S. Chloride ion impact on materials for light-emitting electrochemical cells. *Dalton Trans.* **2014**, *43*, 1961-1964. 458
459
30. Vrieling, E.C.; Gieskes, W.W.C. Silicon Deposition in diatoms: control by the pH inside the silicon deposition vesicle. *J. Phycol.* **1999**, *35*, 548- 559. 460
461
31. Babudri, F.; Cardone, A.; Cioffi, C.T.; Farinola, G.M.; Naso, F.; Ragni, R. A straightforward methodology for the introduction of aryl and vinyl substituents in the 5 or 7 position of 8-hydroxyquinoline. *Synthesis*. 2006, *8*, 462
463
464
1325-1332.
32. Kröger, N.; Deutzmann, R.; Bergsdorf, C.; Sumper, M. Species-specific polyamines from diatoms control silica morphology. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **2000**, *97*, 14133-14138. 465
466
33. De Tommasi, E. Light Manipulation by Single Cells: The Case of Diatoms. *J Spectrosc (Hindawi)* **2016**, 2016, 1-13. 467
34. Martínez-Ramírez, S.; Gutierrez-Contreras, R.; Husillos-Rodríguez, N.; Fernandez-Carrasco, L. In-situ reaction of the very early hydration of C3A-gypsum-sucrose system by Micro-Raman spectroscopy. *Cement Concrete Comp.* **2016**, *73*, 251-256. 468
469
35. Doorn, S.K.; Hupp, J.T. Preresonance Raman studies of metal-to-ligand charge transfer in $(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bipyridine})^{2+}$. In situ bond length changes, force constants, and reorganization energies. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1989**, *11*, 4704-4712. 470
471
36. Lai, S.H.; Ling, J.W.; Huang, Y.M.; Huang, M.J.; Cheng, C.H.; Chen, I.C. Characterization of $\text{Ir}(\text{ppy})_3$ and $[\text{Ir}(\text{ppy})_2 \text{bpy}]^+$ by infrared, Raman spectra and surface - enhanced Raman scattering. *J Raman Spectr.* **2011**, *42*, 472
473
474
332-338.